

Comparison of Haptic Strategies for Human Guidance

Tommaso Lisini Baldi
DIISM
University of Siena
Siena, Italy
tommaso.lisini@unisi.it

Gianluca Paolucci
DSMCSB
University of Rome - Tor Vergata
Roma, Italy
gianluca.paolucci.532380@uniroma2.it

Domenico Prattichizzo
DIISM
University of Siena
Siena, Italy
domenico.prattichizzo@unisi.it

Abstract—This paper compares two human guidance approaches mediated by haptic stimulation. Motion Guidance consists in delivering step-by-step instructions to human users, that respond to commands with specific actions. The Sensory Augmentation approach enriches the human with the knowledge necessary to complete the task using a self-selected strategy. The two approaches were evaluated in a collaborative scenario with couples of participants carrying a bulky object under the sole guidance of haptics. Stimuli were delivered by a haptic belt according to three haptic policies. According to results, both approaches performed well when participants were aware of the direction to the target during the whole trial, supporting the idea of using haptics to convey environmental information to the users.

I. INTRODUCTION

Haptic technology has gained importance in the last 15 years. Its success can be attributed to the intimacy of delivery, unobtrusiveness of wearable devices, and intuitiveness of stimuli, factors that lead to a crescent interest on the development and commercialization of haptic devices. Indeed, haptics can effectively convey useful information and contents, and provide an additional sensory layer to remote communications and virtual/augmented reality environments, complementing audio and visual cues with the rich and emotional component of touch.

A large portion of the available literature investigated the technological aspect of haptic devices, that is, what types of stimuli can be provided and how to make them feel realistic [1]. Instead, we want to understand how to design haptic communication strategies that are compliant with the human behavior to provide support and assistance in daily activities [2].

In particular, we compared the effectiveness of two methodologies: Motion Guidance and Sensory Augmentation. The *Motion Guidance* is a common paradigm used in haptics and inspired from robotics. It refers to the delivery of step-by-step instructions that users enact to achieve their objective. Examples of haptic Motion Guidance applied to navigation of humans are described in [3], [4].

The latter approach, *Sensory Augmentation*, provides the users with the perception of a parameter relevant for the task completion through sensory stimulation. It exploits the human capability to integrate external information about the environment and prior experience to plan the working strategy. For instance, rather than instructing the optimal path to follow, incoming obstacles can be displayed through haptic cues to

Fig. 1: A couple of blindfolded co-workers carries a bulky object guided by haptic stimuli. The guidance exploits three different haptic policies, whose performance are compared in the experimental campaign.

allow the users to modify the motion trajectory [5]. In the current work, participants are provided with haptic stimuli indicating the direction to the target point to reach.

We conducted an experimental campaign where couples of participants performed an object-carrying task, *i.e.* the two users have to move in concert while transporting a bulky object along predefined trajectories (see Fig. 1). The selected task is simple enough to be performed by blindfolded participants that cannot communicate verbally, so they must rely on the haptic guidance only.

The comparison was held between three strategies inspired by motion guidance and sensory augmentation. The first, called *Holonomic Motion Guidance*, delivers instructions about the direction participants have to walk toward. Users are asked to follow the commands and move inside the workspace without changing the orientation of the formation. The *Nonholonomic Motion Guidance* policy provides users with translation and rotation cues, that instruct the users to rotate the formation to reach the target point without walking diagonally. Rotations can be performed on-place or during walk. In this case, people receive two different patterns that encode meaning of translation or rotation. The *Sensory Augmentation* approach entrusts the decision of the walking strategy to the users, and the haptics are used only to display the information that is relevant for the task and otherwise unknown to the users, *i.e.* the direction

to the goal.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

A. Haptic Guidance Policies

Three policies were developed for the purpose of the work. Two of them are inspired from two walking models that diversely address the problem of walking in directions different from the frontal: the holonomic and nonholonomic models. The concept of holonomic and nonholonomic constraints originates from robotics and has been applied to the human walking behavior. Lending the conventions used in [6], [7], in general the human walking is considered a nonholonomic motion. The only exception to the nonholonomic nature in human walking takes place when the point to be reached is close to the human. In that case, it is more convenient to perform lateral or diagonal steps instead of rotating and then taking few steps forward [8]. In the specific context of a formation of humans moving a bulky object, it has to be taken into account that the arrangement of the formation due to the object geometry may force some users to walk backwards or sideward.

In accordance with the aforementioned holonomic and non-holonomic models, two guidance policies were designed, which leveraged patterns of tactile stimuli to provide instructions under the “*Motion Guidance*” paradigm.

The third policy investigated the possibility of improving the task execution by augmenting the human’s perceptions through haptics. Instead of instructing the users to perform specific motions, the haptic interface provides the users with necessary information about the task objective, which are then elaborated and exploited by the members of the formation, relying on their own experience.

Based on these assumptions, the three haptic policies are presented as follows:

Holonomic Motion Guidance (H): Motors continuously vibrate indicating the direction to the goal. The vibration amplitude is proportional to sine and cosine of the direction angle. The user is instructed to perform a translation in the suggested direction. No rotation is allowed. Vibrations are interrupted for 1s at reaching intermediate targets.

Nonholonomic Motion Guidance (N): Users are provided with either of the two different haptic pattern representing the following instructions:

i) *Rotate*: motors vibrate creating a clockwise or counterclockwise wave. The formation has to rotate in the suggested direction. The haptic pattern is active until the frontal direction (of the formation) is close to the target direction, with a $\pm 20^\circ$ tolerance.

ii) *Translate*: motors vibrate to indicate the direction to the target. The vibration amplitude is proportional to sine and cosine of the direction angle. The user is instructed to perform a translation in the suggested direction. Vibrations are interrupted for 1s at reaching intermediate targets.

Sensory Augmentation (SA): Motors continuously vibrate indicating the direction to the goal. The vibration amplitude is

proportional to sine and cosine of the direction angle. The user is instructed to choose the strategy to reach the target. Vibrations are interrupted for 1s at reaching intermediate targets.

The *Holonomic* condition is based on the assumption that the formation is able to travel goal-by-goal while maintaining a fixed orientation, that can be beneficial when transporting objects that require stability.

In the *Nonholonomic* policy, users translate only forward or backward, avoiding lateral steps. Moreover, they are allowed to steer the direction during walk in a nonholonomic way, according to the haptic instructions.

The design of the *Sensory Augmentation* condition took into account the fact that humans are not as precise as robots when it comes to perform a motion, neither they need accurate step-by-step instructions to execute a complex task. Instead, they are able to select the most efficient and natural set of actions to reach a goal, thanks to their experience and innate motion-planning capacity.

Haptic cues were generated using a belt equipped with four vibratory motors placed at the cardinal points of the belt. Directions that do not lay on the frontal or lateral axis are displayed as a combination of two vibrations from adjacent actuators, whose intensity is proportional to cosine and sine of the direction angle.

III. EXPERIMENTS

The experiments were designed to evaluate the task execution performance in the three conditions (H, N, and SA). Additionally, participants’ opinions and subjective evaluations were collected using a post-experiment questionnaire to retrieve valuable information about usability and comfort of the proposed approaches.

Ten participants (5 males, 5 females, age 25-55) took part to the experimental campaign.

The object dimensions were $100 \times 60 \times 90$ cm, its weight was approximately 15kg. To test the three policies, we randomly generated 4 paths, consisting of a starting point, an end point, and three or four breakpoints. The available workspace was a room of about 30m^2 . A Vicon Tracking system equipped with ten Vicon Bonita cameras was used to track the participants.

The threshold of 0.5m beyond which the goal was considered reached was chosen after 12 pilot trials.

During each trial, two blindfolded participants were asked to hold the bulky object and walk along a predefined set of goals while being guided by the haptic cues.

At the end of the experiment, they were asked to fill a questionnaire to evaluate their experience and to provide helpful feedback. The questionnaire¹ was aimed to evaluate qualitative aspects of the experiment: *Ease of use*, *Ease of learning* and *Comfort* regarding the three conditions. Items concerning *Ease of use* and *Ease of learning* derive from the *USE* questionnaire [9]. The items on *Comfort*, instead, have been designed to evaluate the movements naturalness.

¹The questionnaire items are available at <https://www3.diiism.unisi.it/~lisini/questionnaires/USEConf.html>

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

Smoothness of the trajectory, trial execution time, and questionnaires about intuitiveness of the haptic cues and comfort in movements have been taken into account in the comparison of the haptic strategies. The alpha-level adopted for the statistical analyses is $\alpha = 0.05$.

Smoothness: The object trajectories recorded during the trials were analysed to extract meaningful information about the smoothness of the point-to-point movements in the three conditions. The smoothness was calculated for each segment as the standard deviation of the angular velocity around the vertical axis. The Kruskal-Wallis test reported statistical significance. The pairwise comparison were performed using Paired Wilcoxon rank sum test. The difference between Nonholonomic and Sensory Augmentation conditions was statistically significant, while the difference between N and H was not significant. The comparison between Holonomic and Sensory Augmentation conditions obtained a *p-value* slightly larger than the alpha-level used as a reference in the text.

Time: Completion time was used as metric for comparing the effectiveness of the three policies. Both the overall trial time and the time to reach the single target were evaluated. Starting with the overall task time, the average time to perform the trials is depicted in Fig. 2a. Trial durations per condition were analyzed using Shapiro-Wilk test and Levene test to check the normality of distributions and homogeneity of variance, respectively. Both tests were not significant for the considered combination of trials and conditions. The difference between conditions was assessed using One way Repeated Measures ANOVA, taking into consideration the effects of conditions on the trial duration. The test showed a statistically significant effect of the condition on the trial duration. The pairwise t-test performed on the three combinations of conditions showed a statistically significant reduction of the trial duration in the H and SA condition with respect to the N condition. On the other hand, there was no statistical difference between the H and SA trial duration distributions.

For what concerns partial times, the time to travel each segment of the trajectory was normalized by the length of the segment itself in order to compare time values across the trials. Normalized times per condition have been compared using Kruskal-Wallis test. The Kruskal-Wallis test by rank reported a statistically significant difference between groups that was further assessed through a pairwise comparison using the Wilcoxon rank sum test.

The statistical tests showed that the N condition was statistically different from the H and SA conditions, while the difference between H and SA condition was not statistically significant.

Questionnaire: The average rating obtained in each questionnaire subsection (*Ease of use*, *Ease of learning* and *Comfort*) has been used as metric for the comparison.

A statistical analysis was performed on the questionnaire data to assess statistical significance in the three subsections.

	SA	H	N
Destination Available	✓	✓	
Freedom of Motion	✓		
Holonomic Strategy		✓	
Single haptic pattern	✓	✓	
<i>Time-efficiency</i>	✓	✓	
<i>Smoothness</i>	✓		
<i>Ease of Use/Learning</i>	✓	✓	
<i>Comfort</i>	✓		✓

TABLE I: the table rows represent the **independent factors**, in bold, and the *dependent factors*, or measured metrics, in italic. Columns represent the three haptic policies. Checkmarks indicate the feature of each experimental condition (for the independent factors) and high ratings of the measured metrics. Blank spaces indicate absence of features and low scores.

The values obtained from the Likert scale should be treated as ordinals, so we performed a Kruskal-Wallis test for each questionnaire subsection, using the *Condition* (H, N, SA) as independent factor. The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed statistical significance between the rating distributions for the *Ease of Use*, *Ease of Learning*, and *Comfort*.

For what concerns the *Ease of Use*, ratings for the N condition were statistically different from H and SA conditions. The difference between H and SA conditions was not statistically significant. For what concerns the *Ease of Learning*, ratings for the H condition were statistically different from N condition. The SA condition was not statistically different from N and H conditions. For what concerns the *Comfort*, ratings for the H condition were statistically different from N and SA conditions. The difference between N and SA conditions was not statistically significant.

B. Discussion

Considering the three conditions under the different metrics measured in this work, the SA condition was time-efficient, reported the greatest trajectory smoothness, and received high ratings for what concerns *Ease of Use*, *Ease of Learning* and *Comfort*. Condition H was also time-efficient, while the smoothness was intermediate. Scores were high for *Usability* and *Ease of learning*, but low for *Comfort*. The N policy, despite the high *Comfort* ratings, had the worst results for what concerns time-efficiency and smoothness, and received low scores on *Usability* and *Ease of learning*.

In a *posteriori* analysis of the results, we isolated the relevant independent factors that have affected the properties and performance of the three haptic policies: *i*) Continuous Availability of the target direction during the task, *ii*) Freedom of motion, *iii*) Holonomic or Noholonomic walking model, *iv*) Number of haptic patterns. The factors are reported in Table I as rows, whereas columns represent the considered haptic policy. Moreover, we enriched the table with the binary ratings of the exploited metrics, considered *dependent factors*, according to the three conditions.

Fig. 2: Average task-completion times, normalized task-completion times and questionnaire ratings are reported in the plots. * indicates p -value ≤ 0.05 in questionnaire ratings plots.

To extract new insights on the conditions, we expressed the three haptic policies as a combination of the independent factors: SA can be considered a control condition, that allowed participants to always perceive the direction to the goal and to move without constraints. In the H condition the direction to target was always available, but motions were constrained according to the holonomic model (by experimental protocol). In the N condition the direction to target was only partially available due to the presence of rotation cues, and the movement was constrained according to the nonholonomic model.

Results and users' opinions suggest that constraining the movements (despite the model adopted) did not strictly affect the time-efficiency, while the smoothness was affected. Instead, impairing the perception/knowledge of the target direction had a relevant effect on the time to perform the task and on the smoothness of walked trajectories. The Ease of Use and Ease of Learning might be linked to the number of haptic patterns, or, more probably, to the availability of goal location. We interpret this link as the intuitiveness of the haptic cues. In accordance with the literature about the human walking strategies, the condition featuring the holonomic model reported the lower comfort rating. Further works might analyse this aspect in the light of ergonomics or muscular fatigue.

The relevance of the target availability factor suggests that the Sensory Augmentation approach was more suitable than the Motion Guidance approach for assisting the users during the task execution in order to pursue time efficiency and usability of the system. On the other side, the results obtained do not discredit the Motion Guidance paradigm that could be more beneficial whenever the task conditions are more strict, *e.g.* if the users need very precise instructions or the formation is large and requires the supervision of an external leader.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This work investigated the difference between two haptic stimulation paradigms in a cooperative task performed by couples of users. The haptic patterns delivered by the belt were used either to convey instructions about the motions to perform (in the Holonomic and Nonholonomic Motion Guidance conditions) or to display the direction to the objective

(in the Sensory Augmentation condition). In average, the users completed the task more efficiently whenever the direction to the objective was completely available during the trial, *i.e.* in H and SA conditions. Conversely the N condition, due to the presence of the rotation instruction that impaired the knowledge of the target position, reported the lowest overall performance. This result supports the idea that providing essential and straightforward information through the haptic channel allows the users to integrate the additional information as an extension of the perceptive ability. Constraining motions in the Motion Guidance policies affected mostly the smoothness of movements, while the perceived comfort can be correlated to the walking model adopted: the nonholonomic model, that is more often exhibited by humans, was received more positively by participants.

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